

The Roman presbyters and *la bella scrittura Filocaliana*

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The long-standing collaboration between Bishop Damasus of Rome and Furius Dionysius Filocalus has prompted extensive scholarly research over the years, thereby forging a lasting and inseparable link between them. This article does not seek to undermine that bond; rather, it demonstrates – on the basis of surviving epigraphic evidence – that Filocalus’ workshop was not solely Damasus’ domain but was also heavily employed by Roman presbyters. They were the earliest imitators of Damasus’ building initiatives and the most devoted supporters of his project to monumentalize suburban cemeteries, making full use of the recognizable Filocalian script as their primary means of expressing this innovative vision.

The remarkable collaboration between Damasus the poet and Filocalus the calligrapher, which resulted in a corpus of verse epigrams displayed at sites honouring Roman martyrs, has been the focus of intensive scholarly investigation since at least the mid-nineteenth century. During the archaeological excavations of the time, new fragments of Damasan *carmina*, inscribed in Filocalus’ distinctive script – *la bella scrittura Filocaliana*¹ – were unearthed in suburban cemeteries, leaving little doubt about the close partnership between the two. Giovanni Battista de Rossi famously declared that ‘even the smallest fragment marked with these letters is a precious relic of the Damasan text’, and further emphasized that the elegant calligraphy of Furius Dionysius Filocalus was both intended for the metrical inscriptions of the poet-pope and exclusively reserved as Damasus’ own.² De Rossi was so convinced of the inseparable nature of this connection that, in his *La Roma sotterranea*, he argued that after Damasus’

death, Filocalus deliberately refrained from using the script for other commissions. However, this view was contested almost as soon as it gained wide acceptance.³

One of the most influential contributions to this debate came from Antonio Ferrua, who, in his landmark study of Damasan epigrams, extensively explored the relationship between Damasus' poetic inscriptions and Filocalus' script. Ferrua unequivocally argued that not all epigrams indisputably attributed to Damasus – those explicitly 'signed' with the bishop's name at their conclusion – were executed in Filocalus' hand.⁴ For instance, fragmentary epigrams composed in honour of Damasus' mother Laurentia, and sister Irene, were inscribed by an individual whose skill fell far short of that of a master stonecutter.⁵ Likewise, the surviving fragment of Damasus' epigram honouring the martyrs Nereus and Achilleus was inscribed in a script that noticeably deviates from Filocalus' style, particularly in the finishing details of the letters.⁶ To categorize inscriptions that imitated Filocalus' lettering style but diverged in key features – most notably in the design of the serifs – Ferrua introduced the term 'semi-Filocalian script'. While the resemblance to the original can at times be striking, later semi-Filocalian inscriptions from the fifth and sixth centuries lack the meticulous craftsmanship and precision.⁷

In the introduction to his edition of Damasus' works, Ferrua posed a thought-provoking question in his summary: during Damasus' episcopate, when Filocalus was in his service, was 'everything Damasan Filocalian, while anything semi-Filocalian was not Damasan'?⁸ In this article, I propose to take a contrarian perspective and reverse the question: was everything Filocalian necessarily Damasan? And can we truly assert that Damasus had exclusive access to Filocalus' skills, even during the period when the calligrapher was primarily working on commissions only for him?

These questions hinge on the surviving fragments of inscriptions executed in Filocalian script that suggest that it was not Damasus but Roman presbyters who

commissioned them. Such examples are admittedly scarce: three inscriptions preserved only in small fragments, and one, known from a single surviving piece of stone, but fortunately recorded in its entirety in a medieval *sylloge*. While these remnants may seem modest en masse, I argue that they are pivotal. They shift the long-standing debate – ongoing since the nineteenth century – about Filocalus’ body of work in a new direction. These inscriptions challenge the dominant narrative of the calligrapher’s exclusive association with the bishop of Rome, revealing that Filocalus simultaneously undertook ambitious commissions for other members of the Roman clergy.

These fragments provide some of the earliest evidence of a significant development: the presbyters’ growing involvement in the monumentalization of the places of worship. This group of presbyter-builders, who commemorated their work through metrical inscriptions, undoubtedly began forming under Damasus’ leadership during his episcopate. After his death, under the patronage of Siricius (384–99), Anastasius (399–401), and Innocentius (401–17), they expanded their building activities, taking on increasingly ambitious projects.⁹

In this article, I wish to focus on Filocalus’ connections with the Roman presbyters and on their likely commissions carried out during Damasus’ papacy. In the detailed introduction to his edition of Damasan works, Dennis Trout observed that the mere presence of Filocalian script on a fragment ‘typically warrants assigning the stone to a Damasan project’.¹⁰ This perspective is understandably rooted in the fact that most surviving Damasan inscriptions in stone feature Filocalian lettering. However, equating Filocalian script exclusively with Damasus’ building projects is not only an oversimplification but – as we will see below in the case of presbyter Verus’ inscription – obscures the true significance of the text itself.

Although Trout does acknowledge toward the end of his discussion on Filocalus that the presence of his script is neither definitive nor conclusive – citing exceptions first noted by Ferrua¹¹ – this observation did not lead to any deeper conclusions that might have allowed for

a critical reassessment of the widespread theory that Filocalus' workshop worked exclusively for Damasus.

While it is often said that one exception proves the rule, multiple exceptions rule it out. The following epigraphic material demonstrates that the presence of Filocalian script cannot serve as automatic proof of Damasus' patronage. Instead, it suggests that Filocalus, while deeply involved in the pope's monumental projects, also carried out commissions for other members of the ecclesiastical elite, particularly the presbyters.

[A] Furius Dionysius Filocalus: stonemason or calligrapher?

The decision to refer to Filocalus at the very outset of this essay as a calligrapher rather than a stonemason immediately positions the author on one side of a debate that has been ongoing for more than a century – a debate which requires some elaboration. At its core lies the question of whether Filocalus just designed the letters or whether he also carved them into stone with his own hands. Antonio Ferrua, and later Nicolette Gray, supported the latter view.¹² Josep Vives, by contrast, doubted that Filocalus himself cut and sculpted the letters of the Damasan *carmina*.¹³ Dennis Trout expressed the matter more diplomatically, observing that 'certainty in this question is impossible'.¹⁴

In my view, however, it is possible to move closer to certainty by examining the contexts in which terms such as *titulavit*, *scripsit*, and *sculpsit* were used. In the earliest work attesting to Filocalus' activity – the so-called *Chronography of 354* – the verso of the title page bears the inscription: *Furius Dionysius Filocalus titulavit*.¹⁵ As Armando Petrucci has demonstrated, this term, which in a technical sense means 'to place an inscription', here refers to the design of the entire title-page layout, 'conceived and planned as a luxury inscription'.¹⁶

Two inscriptions signed by Filocalus have also survived in which he employs the term *scribere* to describe his work.¹⁷ In his now-classic study of Roman palaeography, Jean

Mallon distinguished between *sculpsit* and *scripsit*, arguing that the former refers to the act of engraving, whereas the latter ‘does not refer to the intellectual preparation of the text, but to its physical preparation on stone, prior to the engraver’s work. This preparation consisted of tracing the outlines in chalk, charcoal, dry point, or brush, which lines would then be followed by the chisel.’¹⁸ The separation of these two processes – design and layout on the one hand, and the actual carving on the other – is well attested in epigraphy.¹⁹

If, then, Filocalus used the term *scripsit*, we may reasonably assume that he personally designed the layout of the letters on the stone, which – contrary to Mallon’s interpretation – could also have involved, to some extent, the intellectual formulation of the text. An open question remains: if we suppose that Filocalus was personally involved in every inscription in the Filocalian script, why does his signature appear on only three examples and not on all? This seems to suggest an occasional practice of signing only selected works.

It is, however, difficult to agree with Petrucci’s categorical verdict, which reduced Filocalus’ role to that of the inventor of a distinctive and unique capital script, asserting firmly that he was neither ‘calligrapher nor scribe, and still less a stonecutter’.²⁰ There is no evidence for such a limitation, whereas Filocalus’ strictly calligraphic craftsmanship becomes evident at first glance in the letters, whose thick and thin strokes correspond precisely to pen movements.²¹ In my opinion, Filocalus must have been personally involved – as a calligrapher – in designing and drawing the letters on stone. Otherwise, if the work had been executed by a specialized workshop of stonecutters, the Filocalian script would likely have had a much longer lifespan in late antique Roman epigraphy, instead of remaining a singular episode. The decisive proof of Filocalus’ key role in the entire process of inscription-making is the fact that after his death, despite the efforts of stonecutters clearly imitating his script, *la bella scrittura filocaliana* already belonged to the past.

[A] The *elogium* of presbyter Verus for the martyrs Felix and Audactus

One of the most intriguing inscriptions attesting to the building activities of a presbyter within the circle of Damasus is the epigram in honour of the martyr brothers Felix and Audactus²² in the Commodilla cemetery near the *via Ostiensis*.²³ The sanctuary of these martyrs was located in what archaeologists designate as Gallery B, and all the evidence suggests that the initial monumentalization of the site took place during the episcopate of Damasus. Archaeological investigations have located the graves of Felix and Audactus on the north wall of the hypogeal basilica, where two *loculi* – one above the other – are still visible within a niche decorated with several successive layers of painted ornament.²⁴ The proposed reconstruction of the intervention envisages the monumentalization of the entrance to the venerated area – situated immediately before the graves – as well as the zone directly adjoining them. This arrangement comprised an arch with a barrier bearing a metrical inscription; two small columns with an architrave framed the wall into which the martyrs' graves were set, above which was a lunette with a painted image of the patron saints.²⁵ While the precise original appearance of the intervention cannot be established with certainty, it is beyond doubt that the works were crowned with a metrical inscription, which read:

O Felix, twice fortunate in your true name, with flawless faith,

despising the prince of the world,

you confessed Christ and sought out the celestial realms.

O truly precious faith of a brother – recognize it! –

by which Audactus likewise rushed to heaven, a victor.

On their behalf the presbyter Verus, in accord with the wishes of Damasus the bishop,

arranged their tomb, adorning the dwelling of the saints.²⁶

The above text is the earliest evidence of the veneration of these martyrs, whose names do not appear in the *Depositio Martyrum* – the oldest list of Roman martyrs.²⁷ Since their cult

is not attested there, it may be inferred that the monumentalization of the *loculi*, together with the commemoration of their martyrdom in an epigram, played a decisive role in the diffusion and popularization of their veneration. Later passages from several written sources as well as numerous preserved graffiti, suggest that in subsequent centuries the martyrs' tomb and the underground basilica were significant landmarks on the map of Rome, popular among pilgrims not only from the Italian Peninsula but also beyond the Alps.²⁸

This epigram has been preserved in several medieval *syllogae*,²⁹ but a fragment of the original stone has also survived, identified by de Rossi (Fig. 1). While examining inscriptions in the Vatican collections, de Rossi recognized, in the Philocalian script, fragments of an epigram that had been placed at the tomb of Felix and Audactus.³⁰ Thus, the text displays both linguistic features and stylistic turns characteristic of Damasus, together with surviving examples of Philocalian lettering – two criteria that have consistently led modern editors to classify this *elogium* among the *carmina* of Damasus.³¹

[Place Fig. 1 around here]

The text leaves no doubt that the commissioner of the work – comprising the monumentalization of the martyrs' tomb (*tumulus*), formed by two *loculi* placed one above the other – was the presbyter Verus, who states this explicitly, adopting, as Damasus himself does in his own compositions, the third person singular (*Presbyter his Verus (. . .) composuit tumulum*). Verus further describes his intervention at the tomb of Felix and Audactus as 'adorning the thresholds of the saints' (*sanctorum limina adornans*).

It thus appears evident from the text that the monumentalization of the space around the *loculi* of Felix and Audactus was carried out through the intervention of the presbyter Verus. This, however, raises further questions – namely, whether the preserved *carmen* should be considered the work of Damasus or rather of the presbyter Verus, and, more broadly, what the epigram reveals about Damasus' involvement in the undertaking.

The latter question can be addressed through archaeological evidence, which attributes to the period of Damasus' episcopate an extensive building campaign in Gallery B of the *region arenarium*, where the remains of the martyrs Felix and Audactus were likely deposited during the persecutions under Valerian or Diocletian.³² The works included the widening of the corridor in the northern section of which the martyrs' graves were located. The *elogium*, however, mentions only the arrangement of the tomb itself – presumably the most important and central element of the intervention.³³ It is therefore plausible that Damasus, having initiated the redevelopment and monumentalization of this area, at some point enlisted the presbyter Verus to take charge of the project's focal point: the arrangement of the tomb of Felix and Audactus, which Verus subsequently commemorated in the metrical verses of the *elogium*.

This interpretation seems to be supported by the phrase *Damaso rectore iubente*, which sheds light on the relationship between the bishop of Rome and the presbyter. The verb *iubente* can, of course, be translated as 'by order' or 'at the command' of Damasus, which would reduce Verus' role to that of an executor of the pope's initiatives. Yet why, in that case, would Damasus later record Verus' involvement in precisely the same manner in which he described his own, employing the third person singular? This seems improbable, especially given that Damasus almost never acknowledged in his verses the involvement of others in his projects – essentially only once, in the epigram commemorating the drainage and channelling of spring waters on the Vatican Hill, overseen by the deacon Mercurius (*haec curavit Mercurius levita fidelis*).³⁴

In my view, *Damaso rectore iubente* is better understood as 'at the encouragement' or 'with the permission' of Bishop Damasus – a subtle difference, yet one that harmonizes with the overall sense the author of the *elogium* sought to convey. Verus would thus have been the one who monumentalized the martyrs' tomb, having first been encouraged or authorized to do

so by Damasus. Whether the initiative originated with the pope or with the presbyter himself cannot be determined; both scenarios are equally plausible. It is possible that Verus requested permission to undertake the most important task in the building campaign at the Commodilla catacombs – the monumentalization of the area around the *loculi* of Felix and Audactus. Conversely, Damasus may have encouraged his presbyters to take an active role in the embellishment of cult sites.

Whatever the identity of the *spiritus movens* behind Verus' intervention at the Commodilla cemetery, the formula *presbyter his Verus Damaso rectore iubente composuit tumulum* is nothing less than an exact reflection of the degree of involvement of each party: the tomb was arranged by the presbyter Verus, acting at the encouragement or with the permission of Bishop Damasus.

If the commissioner of the works at the tomb of Felix and Audactus was the presbyter Verus, the question remains: to whom should the *elogium*, fragments of which survive in the Philocalian script, be attributed? The script itself leaves no doubt that the inscription was executed in the workshop of Filocalus. What is less certain is whether Verus composed the verses of the epigram himself or whether he requested Damasus to do so. The text, however, unmistakably bears the hallmarks of Damasus' style. Phrases such as *princeps mundi* to denote the adversary of humankind, *confitieri Christum*, *intemerata fide*, and the epithet *victor* applied to the martyr occur repeatedly in other *elogia* attributed to him.³⁵ Such parallels inevitably invite the argument that the poem must be Damasus' own composition, reusing literary turns of phrase he already favoured. Verus, working in collaboration with Damasus on a common project, may have invited the bishop to compose an epigram on his behalf.

Even if we were to accept that Damasus authored the verses in honour of Felix and Audactus, the poem would still acknowledge Verus as the actual commissioner of the

building works, while limiting Damasus' role to that of an inspirer. This would be a striking precedent within the corpus of Damasan *carmina*, which are distinguished, among other things, by Damasus' practice of 'signing' his poems in the third person.

In my view, the appearance in the *elogium* of the formulae characteristic of Damasus' poetry could just as well suggest that Verus himself composed the verses, deliberately imitating the literary style of his bishop. Such derivative practice would also serve as a form of homage to his superior's achievements in this field. The use of the term *rector* with reference to Damasus may point to precisely this special relationship between master and disciple. While *rector* appears several times in the epigrams of Damasus as one of the titles of his office,³⁶ in a more colloquial sense it also denotes a teacher, guide, or one who imparts both knowledge and craft. It is therefore conceivable that Verus, as a presbyter closely accompanying the bishop of Rome in the commemoration of the martyrs, observing his methods and style of honouring them, eventually desired to undertake such a task himself. Having secured Damasus' approval – or indeed his encouragement – he proceeded to intervene at the *sanctorum limina*.

Damasus, for his part, was well aware that Verus possessed the financial means to carry out the project. As a presbyter closely associated with him, Verus also had direct access to Filocalus – if not personally, then certainly through the protection and backing of the bishop. Filocalus, as Alan Cameron has argued, most likely belonged to the urban elite, as did his clients: Valentinus, the dedicatee of the *Chronograph of 354*, and later Damasus himself. Epigraphic evidence also suggests possible links between Filocalus and Melania the Elder.³⁷ These connections indicate that Filocalus' workshop was not an ordinary stonecutting atelier catering to the masses, but a highly prestigious establishment serving an exclusive clientele of similar social standing – precisely the milieu to which Verus belonged.

The Damasan epigrams, although among the most valuable sources for the history of the monumentalization of Roman martyr shrines, are in large measure monuments to the glory of a single individual: Damasus himself. Their testimony does not allow us to reconstruct in detail the building processes they celebrate, which necessarily involved dozens of participants, all but effaced by the truth of the adage *scripta manent*. The intervention of the presbyter Verus at the tomb of Felix and Audactus in the Commodilla cemetery illuminates this process, showing that construction and monumentalization at the suburban cemeteries were by no means the work of a single man, as Damasus' *elogia* might naively suggest, but rather the outcome of collegial collaboration between the pope and selected members of his clergy.

[Place Fig. 2 around here]

The existence of such a group of presbyters who carried out their own foundations during the episcopate of Damasus, and who explicitly invoked their ties with him, is confirmed – besides the case of Verus – by the epigram of the presbyter Leo from the cemetery of Hippolytus on the *via Tiburtina*³⁸ (Fig. 2). In this inscription, Leo presents himself as the patron of works undertaken on the surrounding structures (*moenia crescunt*), in a place he designates as the *domus martyris Ippoliti*, most probably referring to the hypogeal sanctuary arranged at the martyr's tomb.³⁹ Leo further emphasizes that 'the adornments of the work rise under the guidance of Damasus, who was born as bishop of the Apostolic See'. The text clearly indicates that the underground sanctuary dedicated to Hippolytus underwent its initial phase of intervention at the instigation of Damasus, whereas an additional foundation – described in general terms as *haec omnia nova* – was the work of the presbyter Leo.

The epigram, now preserved within the catacombs of San Ippolito and reassembled from several stone fragments, was certainly not executed by Filocalus. Antonio Ferrua described the surviving letters as *vulgares et non accuratae*.⁴⁰ In my view, however, the

inscription of the presbyter Leo is not the original but rather a sixth-century copy. A palaeographic analysis of the script in which the *elogium* is written, when compared with, for example, the sixth-century copy of Damasus' *elogium* for Eusebius, reveals striking similarities.⁴¹ In both cases the letters display comparable length and breadth, the treatment of vertex terminals, the layout on the stone, and the spacing between both letters and lines. If, therefore, the preserved *elogium* of the presbyter Leo from the cemetery of Hippolytus on the *via Tiburtina* – dating with certainty to the episcopate of Damasus – is indeed a sixth-century copy, we can only conjecture what the original may have looked like, though it cannot be excluded that it too was executed in the refined Philocalian script.

The examples of Verus and Leo – wealthy presbyter-benefactors acting under the inspiration of their bishop – demonstrate with striking clarity that Damasus had gathered around himself a circle of presbyters endowed with the requisite abilities, qualifications, and, above all, the financial means that enabled them not only to undertake interventions at cult sites independently, but also, in due course, to carry forward on their own the monumentalization he had set in motion. What Damasus imparted to them was nothing less than a comprehensive repertoire of cultural and technical resources: a precise literary model from which they could draw inspiration, and privileged access to trusted and proven craftsmen who ensured the execution of their projects to the highest standard.

Both inscriptions – that of Verus and that of Leo – emphasize the connection of their undertakings with Damasus, though Leo goes considerably further, expressing frank devotion and admiration for his achievements. Leo allows himself a rhetoric clearly imbued with ideological colouring: according to him, Damasus was ‘born to preside over the Apostolic See’ and pursued his enterprises ‘amid peaceful triumphs’. In the context of Damasus’ episcopate and his often combative policy towards opponents, such claims amount, if not to a

conscious reimagining of reality, then at least to the hyperbolic flattery of a loyal partisan whose ecclesiastical career was closely bound to the bishop's favour.

Nonetheless, the motives that led both presbyters to realize their own projects at the tombs of martyrs may well have been similar. Both were trusted associates of Damasus who accompanied him in the initiatives undertaken at the martyr shrines, and who, at a certain point, wished to contribute their own share to this vast programme. Naturally, this was done with the encouragement – or at the very least the approval – of Damasus himself, whose role as inspirer was later acknowledged in poetic form. Yet despite this role, the foundations described in these epigrams were, in the final analysis, the works of the presbyters themselves.

[A] Filocalus and presbyter Theodorus

Another testament to Filocalus' collaboration with a Roman presbyter comes from the fragments of a heavily damaged inscription discovered in 1917 at the cemetery of Pontianus on the *via Portuensis* (Fig. 3).⁴² The inscription was executed in the Filocalian script, though the noticeable thickening on the lower stems of certain letters (particularly R and H), as well as visible imperfections in the execution of the triple serifs, suggest some technical shortcomings, caused either by Filocalus himself – at a time when his refined craftsmanship was beginning to give way to waning strength – or by a less careful stonecutter. The fragments found at the time, preserving the same lettering style, include partial sculptural decoration characteristic of marble *plutei*. The inscription itself was positioned at the upper section of the panels. Three fragments contain the words: *BYTER HOS* (a), *ORUS* (b), and *R HONORE* (c).

[Place Fig. 3 around here]

Orazio Marucchi proposed the following reconstruction: (Fig. 3, fragment no. 2) *[pres]byter hos (...) orus d[---]*; (Fig. 3, fragment no. 3) *[propte]r honore[m]*.⁴³ Ferrua largely agreed with this reconstruction but firmly rejected the suggestion that fragment (b) could be completed as *[Theod]orus*, citing insufficient space for five additional letters.⁴⁴ He was similarly sceptical of reconstructing the first letter following *orus* as D, pointing out that the single vertical stroke could correspond to several other letters. Decades later, however, while revising the inscriptions from the cemetery of Pontianus, he unexpectedly proposed a new reconstruction of the line: *[pres]byter hos [Theod]orus d[onate]r honore[m]*, though he did not provide any explanation for this reversal.⁴⁵

Ferrua's earlier objections from 1942 were, of course, unfounded. In the photographs published by Marucchi (Fig. 3), fragment (b), with the preserved word *orus*, had been connected to fragment (a), *[pres]byter hos*, but this was a secondary assembly; originally the fragments may have been further apart. Marucchi, in his publication of these fragments, suggested that they formed part of a balustrade placed in front of the tomb of the cemetery's most famous martyrs, Abdon and Sennes.⁴⁶ According to tradition, these Persian saints were executed in Rome during the reign of Decius, and later, during Constantine's reign, their bodies were raised up and translated to the cemetery of Pontianus. Their veneration was first recorded in the *Depositio Martyrum*.⁴⁷ The site of their burial at the cemetery of Pontianus became a popular destination for pilgrims, as attested by seventh-century itineraries.⁴⁸ If the demonstrative pronoun *hos* indeed refers to these two martyrs (and it is difficult to imagine another plausible interpretation), this would constitute the second-earliest known evidence not only of their cult, but also of monumentalization efforts at their tomb.

Who, then, was the author of these works? If we assume that the disputed fragment (b) represents the ending of a name, several interpretative possibilities arise. The Filocalian letters leave no doubt that it was created during the episcopate of Damasus. Among all the names

that could fit the ending *-orus*, none aligns as convincingly as *Theodorus* – there was a presbyter of this name, well known for his building activity, and amply documented in epigraphic material.

The only fully preserved epigram (available both in its entirety in a *sylloge* and partially in stone) attests to his work at the tomb of the martyrs Protus and Hyacinth in the cemetery of Bassilla ad Hermetem on the *via Salaria vetus* (Fig. 4).⁴⁹ This inscription commemorates the construction of a monumental descent (*descensum*) and includes Theodorus' 'signature' as the author of the project: *hoc Theodorus opus construxit presbyter instans*. Other fragmentary epigraphic evidence suggests that Theodorus also participated in construction work at the Basilica of St Valentine on the *via Flaminia*,⁵⁰ as well as *intra muros* at the titular church of San Lorenzo in Lucina.⁵¹ His involvement in the monumentalization of St Hermes' tomb in the cemetery of Bassilla cannot be ruled out either.⁵²

[Place Fig. 4 around here]

Before assuming that Theodorus was indeed the author of the monumental interventions at the cemetery of Pontianus – attested by the surviving fragments of the inscription – it is necessary to determine whether this presbyter could in fact have had any contact with Filocalus' workshop. The activity of Theodorus is generally situated at the turn of the episcopates of Damasus (366–84) and Siricius (384–99), with a prevailing view that his building work at sites of cult took place after the former's death.⁵³ Charles Pietri, in his opus magnum, *Roma Christiana*, already stressed that Theodorus' foundation at the cemetery of Bassilla *ad Hermetem* – namely, the construction of the monumental descent mentioned above – must belong to the pontificate of Siricius. Pietri argued that 'contemporary practice would not have permitted a cleric to proclaim his own glory during the lifetime of Damasus, without reference to the pope as the initiator of the enterprise'.⁵⁴ By contrast, in

the *Prosopographie chrétienne du Bas-Empire* Theodorus' entry states that he 'most probably acted under the pontificate of Pope Damasus, as indicated by a metrical inscription in the Filocalian style'.⁵⁵ Pietri never explained his later volte-face. Yet the categorical claim that Theodorus could not have undertaken foundations of his own is difficult to sustain for several reasons. The descent described in his *elogium* has happily survived to the present day: what we see is a solid, professionally executed structure. Could Theodorus – having secured the requisite craftsmen, equipment, and, most importantly, financial means – have not commemorated his name in verse out of fear of offending Damasus? Pietri's argument, which suggests this is the case, suffers from two serious flaws. First, it imputes pettiness to Damasus; second, it is logically inconsistent. According to this reasoning, a Roman presbyter could not *chanter sa propre louange* during the episcopate of Damasus, yet could do so under Siricius? There is no evidence to support such a claim.

Theodorus' activity is usually placed under Siricius primarily because of the characteristic 'semi-Filocalian' script preserved in several inscriptions, including the only consularly dated one – namely, the funerary *elogium* of Eventius (*Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum* VI, no. 41377),⁵⁶ dating to 407. The same script is found in two further inscriptions commemorating building works attributed to Theodorus. The first is a fragment associated with the cemetery or basilica of St Valentine on the *via Flaminia*,⁵⁷ in which Orazio Marucchi reconstructed the words *presbyter instans* – a phrase also occurring in Theodorus' inscription for the descent at the cemetery of Bassilla *ad Hermetem* (Fig. 4). On this basis, Marucchi suggested that Theodorus might also have been responsible for the foundation at San Valentino. The second example, inscribed in the same semi-Filocalian script, is the aforementioned inscription from San Lorenzo in Lucina (Fig. 5). Thus, it is above all the palaeographical evidence – dating securely to the turn of the fourth and fifth centuries – that anchors Theodorus' activity in the episcopate of Siricius. Unlike presbyter

Leopardus, who is explicitly attested both in the *Liber Pontificalis* and in the letters of Siricius to Ambrose, there are no direct textual sources documenting Theodorus' activity under Siricius.

[Place Fig. 5 around here]

Nevertheless, if it is nearly certain that Theodorus carried out the bulk of his mature building activity under Siricius, the question remains as to when precisely his 'career' as a founder began – a career that must already have commenced during Damasus' tenure. Unlike Verus and Leo, Theodorus makes no explicit reference to Damasus. Since the content is thus ambiguous, we must turn to palaeography. The inscription commemorating the construction of the descent leading to the *loculi* of Protus and Hyacinth was executed in a script that reveals unmistakable affinities with Filocalian lettering: the pronounced breadth of the letters, the carefully executed 'shading' (i.e. the modulation of stroke thickness), and the elongated serifs crowning the vertical *hastae*. What is lacking are the distinctive undulating serifs of Filocalus, which create swelling in the vertical strokes. Yet in some letters we discern tentative attempts at imitation.

[Place Fig. 6a and 6b around here]

This script is palaeographically strikingly close to that of Damasus' *elogium* for the martyrs Nereus and Achilleus in the catacombs of Domitilla (Fig. 6a and 6b). The two original fragments that survive from this epigram display a script that differs from the finest Filocalian examples, yet at the same time reveals strong similarities – leading Ferrua to date it to the very end of Damasus' pontificate.⁵⁸ The letter forms and their terminals, especially the elongated but non-undulating serifs, make it plausible that both the *elogium* for Nereus and Achilleus and Theodorus' descent inscription were produced by the same hand, or at least by the same workshop – most likely by pupils and collaborators of Filocalus who, after the master's death, continued to execute commissions for Damasus and his presbyters.

The palaeographical affinities between these inscriptions strongly suggest that they were produced within a relatively short span of time. It cannot be excluded, therefore, that Theodorus' foundation at the cemetery of Bassilla *ad Hermetem* coincided with, or followed soon after, Damasus' work at the tomb of Nereus and Achilleus. In any case, Theodorus' mature founding activity – exemplified in the construction of the monumental descent – began and developed under Damasus. The wording of his inscription itself makes this more than evident. Pilgrims visiting the tombs of Protus and Hyacinth would first have read (or heard recited) Damasus' epigram declaring that 'the tomb was hidden deep within the hill's massive bulk',⁵⁹ and then encountered the same motif in Theodorus' *elogium*, which recounts that their graves 'for a long time the mountain, earth, and darkness had covered'. The allusion to Damasus' epigram could hardly be clearer. The foundation itself – the construction of a monumental descent facilitating access to the martyrs' graves, discovered not long before by Damasus – together with this literary echo, appears as a deliberate homage of pupil to master.

Damasus' *elogium* for Protus and Hyacinth deserves particular attention. The left portion of the marble plaque has survived. Ferrua observed that the letter forms exhibit recognizably Filocalian features, though they are less broad than usual.⁶⁰ Indeed, the script of the surviving fragment falls short of the highest standard of Filocalian calligraphy. The characteristic modulation of thick and thin strokes is absent, and the undulating serifs are less carefully executed. It may well be that Filocalus designed this epigram for Damasus when already advanced in years, shortly before his death – just as with the inscription at the tomb of Abdon and Sennes, executed at the request of Theodorus. Both scripts – that of Damasus' *elogium* for Protus and Hyacinth and that of the Pontianus fragments – still display recognizably Filocalian traits, but they lack the old master's brilliance.

We have, therefore, discussed two pairs of inscriptions commemorating building interventions: those of Damasus for Protus and Hyacinthus and (hypothetically) of Theodorus

for Abdon and Sennes, both executed in Filocalus' script; and Damasus' *elogium* for Nereus and Achilleus and Theodorus' inscription celebrating the construction of the descent, produced by a member of the Filocalian workshop (whether a pupil or perhaps a direct successor). Taken together they allow us to draw several conclusions.

First, at the very moment when Damasus was commissioning his own foundations, commemorated in his epigrams (such as that for Protus and Hyacinth in the cemetery of Bassilla *ad Hermetem*), presbyters in his circle were already undertaking their own projects in the suburban cemeteries – for instance, Theodorus at the cemetery of Pontianus. These presbyters, embarking on their 'careers' as founders, secured access to Filocalus' prestigious workshop, hitherto reserved for papal commissions. It is highly plausible that one of Theodorus' first foundations in the suburban cemeteries, during Damasus' lifetime, was precisely that at the cemetery of Pontianus – likely among the last works executed by Filocalus himself, as suggested by the minor workshop imperfections noted above.

Second, as the inscriptions for Nereus and Achilleus and for the descent show, after Filocalus' death both Damasus and the presbyters – including Theodorus – turned to craftsmen who had inherited the calligrapher's workshop or had been his direct pupils.

Third, just as the example of Verus reveals gentle yet unmistakably Damasan supervision over presbyterial projects, so the activity of Theodorus illustrates how swiftly presbyter-benefactors attained independence in their initiatives. Verus exemplifies the preparatory phase, when Damasus was just beginning to encourage – indeed to spur – the clergy to take on such roles. Theodorus, however, represents the full realization of Damasus' vision: presbyters capable not only of carrying forward his projects but also of initiating new ones independently. Theodorus' inscription reveals that he was conducting his own enterprises in parallel with Damasan foundations, employing the same workshop resources as his master.

Damasus himself must have been acutely aware that the projects he had set in motion would require capable successors if the shadowy martyria were to be transformed into architectural complexes able to accommodate pilgrims. To this end, he recruited and prepared members of his immediate circle to assume these responsibilities. From Damasus the presbyters received not only *carte blanche* for their initiatives but also privileged access to the tried-and-tested workshop of Filocalus, thereby guaranteeing continuity for the Damasan legacy. The involvement of Filocalus in clerical foundations – those of Verus, Theodorus, and possibly Leo – is most clearly demonstrated by the fact that, after his death,⁶¹ presbyters under Siricius' episcopate continued to draw on his legacy by employing his pupils and imitators. In this way, presbyters and stonecutters together ensured the perpetuation of the ideals first given tangible form by the collaboration between Damasus and Filocalus.

[A] Filocalus and a presbyterial foundation at San Lorenzo in Lucina

Evidence for Filocalus' collaboration with yet another presbyter from the circle of Damasus may also be provided by a small fragment (19 × 16 cm), discovered in 1872 in a building adjacent to the basilica of San Lorenzo in Lucina and inscribed in carefully executed Filocalian letters (Fig. 7). Preserved are portions of two words from the upper and lower lines – *opra* [---] and *resb* [---] – which have prompted attempts at reconstruction. Maximilian Ihm, in his commentary on the edition of this fragment, suggested the completion [*Christo pra[estante] [---] [p]resb[byter]*], though he acknowledged that this reconstruction offers little insight into the original text.⁶² Ferrua later proposed *pra[ecepta secutus] [p]resb[byter instans]*, noting that the dense arrangement of letters suggests this fragment may represent the final portions of two distinct lines.⁶³ Reconstruction efforts were further complicated by the fact that, despite Giovanni Battista de Rossi's thorough searches, no connection could be

established between the fragment preserved in stone and any known Damasan *elogium* recorded in medieval codices.⁶⁴

[Place Fig. 7 around here]

It is difficult to determine with certainty the original placement of the inscription. Ferrua offered two possibilities: first, that the inscription was located in the *titulus* and commemorated Damasus' election as bishop, which, according to the *Collectio Avellana*, took place in *Lucinis*.⁶⁵ This location is believed to pre-date the earliest known church at the site, whose construction is attributed to Pope Sixtus III (432–40). The second possibility is that the inscription was later relocated to the church from one of the nearby suburban cemeteries.

Despite the challenges of reconstructing the text, the preserved word *resb* in the lower line strongly points to the original inclusion of the term *presbyter*, which could, in turn, suggest the author and patron of the inscription. Could this have been one of the presbyters serving in the titular church? This cannot be ruled out, nor can the possibility that a presbyter, ordained by Damasus, sought to commemorate the place where the bishop was elected to lead the Roman church. Among these various probabilities, one conclusion remains clear: the inscription was crafted by Filocalus – its surviving letters are a masterful example of the stonemason's skill *at its finest*.

Another discovery from San Lorenzo in Lucina, previously mentioned in connection with presbyter Theodorus, might offer further insight into the identity of the patron. This second inscription, a fragment unearthed in January 2001, had been repurposed as part of the upper section of a western window above the vault of the basilica's fifteenth-century sacristy. The reconstructed words read: [---] *a est vitae Christi d[---] [---f?]ontem Theodorus p[resbyter ---?]*.⁶⁶ The reconstruction of the word *fontem* led Olof Brandt, who published the inscription, to suggest that it may originally have been placed in the basilica's baptistery,

which was dismantled in the fifteenth century and later incorporated into the building's structure.

If Brandt's hypothesis is correct, the significance of this inscription extends beyond confirming the foundation; it also serves as evidence of presbyter Theodorus' activities at the site.⁶⁷ Associating Theodorus with San Lorenzo in Lucina is not without merit. Considering his documented work at suburban cemeteries along the *via Salaria Vetus* and *via Flaminia*, the inscription found at San Lorenzo in Lucina may suggest a connection between these cemetery complexes and the basilica, which was situated relatively close to them.

Can the fragmentary inscription containing the word *[p]resb[yster]* also be attributed to the activity of Theodorus? Palaeography complicates such a hypothesis. As noted above, the letters are executed with great precision, far more competently than those on the inscription from the cemetery of Pontianus. It must have been designed by Filocalus at the height of his career. But did Theodorus already have access to his workshop at that stage? Perhaps – though there is no way of demonstrating this with any degree of certainty.

What seems much more plausible is that the inscription was commissioned by some presbyter of Damasus' circle, not necessarily Theodorus himself, whose activity clearly belongs to the later phase of Filocalus' life. Whether this foundation was carried out in a suburban cemetery or directly at the *titulus* is of secondary importance, though one cannot exclude the tantalizing possibility that a presbyter attached to San Lorenzo in Lucina sought to commemorate in this way the very site of Damasus' election to the Apostolic See.

Amidst so many uncertainties and fragile conjectures, one point emerges with relative clarity: the inscription represents yet another commission executed by Filocalus on behalf of a Roman presbyter, commemorating a foundation of some kind. The seven Filocalian letters carved in marble – however uncertain their provenance – remain a further testimony to

Filocalus' close involvement in presbyterial projects, which gathered momentum under the episcopate of Damasus.

[A] Filocalus and the *titulus sepulchralis* of presbyter Timoteus

The final piece of evidence attesting to Filocalus' involvement in commissions for presbyters is a fragment of a small marble tablet measuring 37 x 43 cm, discovered by de Rossi in 1882 in the crypt of Hippolytus at the cemetery on the *via Tiburtina* (Fig. 8). The inscription preserves two words across two lines: *Timoteus presbyter*.⁶⁸ As de Rossi described it, the tablet was found on the steps of the bema in the crypt of the martyr Hippolytus – steps that were covered with a variety of marbles. However, the tablet was originally situated on the front of a nearby *arcosolium*.⁶⁹ De Rossi attributed this change in location to the reconstruction of the entire crypt initiated by Pope Vigilius after it had been heavily damaged during the Gothic siege of Rome in 537. The reuse of broken marble fragments during the restoration of tombs at this cemetery is well documented in the epigraphic record,⁷⁰ making it highly likely that the marble tablet was repurposed as a step during these repairs.

[Place Fig. 8 around here]

The dimensions and arrangement of the words suggest that the tablet was a funerary plaque, likely crowning a tomb niche, rather than part of a larger epigram commemorating an unspecified foundation. Unfortunately, nothing is known about Timoteus himself, aside from the fact that he was a presbyter. His name does not appear in any other sources from this period. What is certain, however, is that the inscription was cut in Filocalian script, and that the crypt at Hippolytus' tomb was the focus of building interventions both during Damasus' episcopate and later under his successors, when presbyters added foundations of their own.⁷¹

At the same time that de Rossi discovered the funerary tablet of presbyter Timoteus, fragments of another monumental inscription in Filocalian script were unearthed in the crypt. Unfortunately, this second inscription was so fragmentary that any attempt at reconstructing the text was impossible.⁷² However, other fragments of marble bearing Filocalian script were identified as belonging to the well-known *elogium* of Damasus for Hippolytus, preserved in the *sylloge*.

All these accounts highlight that the monumentalization of this site, undertaken during the episcopate of Damasus, was a large-scale effort in which Filocalus actively participated, completing several commissions. It is plausible that presbyter Timoteus, possibly acting under Damasus' direction, played some role in the ongoing projects. However, Timoteus appears to have passed away during or shortly after the work, dying before either Damasus or Filocalus. In the absence of additional sources and given the brevity of the inscription, it is difficult to draw firm conclusions about Timoteus' relationship with these two figures. Nevertheless, the inscription itself – executed by the period's foremost epigraphic workshop – offers some intriguing clues.

First, the dimensions of Timoteus' funerary plaque are particularly notable. They are too small for a typical *lastra marmorea* intended to fully cover a *loculus*. Instead, the plaque likely served as a more decorative feature of the tomb. This practice was relatively common, where the *loculus* was sealed using a mix of materials, and the inscription was confined to a small marble plate. This choice was, of course, dictated by the cost of this material. In Christian catacombs, there are numerous examples demonstrating how much cheaper materials were employed to imitate it effectively.⁷³ However, despite its modest scale, great care was taken to enhance its aesthetic appeal through the use of Filocalian script.

This decision implies that the individual who commissioned the plaque from Filocalus' workshop – whether Timoteus himself during his lifetime or a close associate after his death –

belonged to the elite urban aristocracy, a group deeply influenced by artistic culture and committed to specific aesthetic values. The patron would have either possessed the financial means to fund such a commission or, more likely in my view, had a personal connection with Filocalus. The latter scenario suggests that Filocalus undertook this relatively modest commission not as a major project but out of personal acquaintance, or perhaps even friendship, with the presbyter.

This is supported by the fact that very few funerary inscriptions for members of the Roman clergy executed in Filocalian script have survived (and even fewer for members of the secular urban elite). An intriguing exception is a collective funerary inscription – unfortunately highly fragmentary – that includes Filocalus’ ‘signature’ and the date of the deposition of the deceased, who (based on the available evidence) appear to have belonged to the lower ranks of the Roman clergy (Fig. 9).⁷⁴ The absence of references to Damasus, which are present in the other two inscriptions bearing Filocalus’ signature,⁷⁵ suggests that this may have been a private commission by a member of the urban elite. However, as Ferrua observed, Filocalus does not reference his connection to Damasus here, which reinforces idea that this was a private funerary inscription.

[Place Fig. 9 around here]

A similar interpretation can be applied, I believe, to Timoteus’ inscription. Although it is unsigned, Filocalus’ distinctive hand is unmistakably evident. Thus, while the funerary inscription for presbyter Timoteus may not provide substantial insights into late antique prosopography, it does shed valuable light on Filocalus’ connections with the Roman presbyterial community, particularly those involved in construction projects at suburban cemeteries. Filocalus’s active association with this circle – regarded as comprising the custodians and continuators of Damasian ideas – was, to a large extent, a natural consequence

of the attachment and esteem he felt for Damasus; he himself made this explicit, signing himself as Damasus' *cultor atque amator*.⁷⁶

[A] Conclusions

To conclude, it is worth revisiting the provocatively inverted question: was everything Filocalian necessarily Damasan? I have sought to demonstrate, through an analysis of surviving epigraphic evidence, that Filocalus' renowned workshop eventually came to serve Roman presbyters closely associated with Damasus. These presbyters, who likely began as observers and assistants, soon emerged as the first imitators of his legacy. It is reasonable to imagine that, as the formal custodians and continuators of Damasan ideals, they enjoyed privileged access to Filocalus' workshop.

The epigraphic evidence presented here, documenting the presbyters' acts of patronage at sites of worship, demonstrates clearly that they carried forward Damasus' vision by employing the same forms of expression. Beyond the explicit literary references to Damasan poetry, as exemplified by the foundation of presbyter Verus, the most distinctive element was their use of Filocalian script – the defining hallmark of Damasan works.

In a broader context, this dossier captures the earliest stages of the Roman presbyterial community emerging as builders and benefactors of sacred sites, both *intra* and *extra muros*. This phenomenon, which began to take shape in the late fourth century, fully developed at the turn of the fourth and fifth centuries. It represents a crucial phase in understanding the enduring influence of Damasan or Damasan-Filocalian traditions. The intellectual and aesthetic affinities between the presbyters and the works of Filocalus and Damasus resonated deeply in subsequent decades, particularly during the episcopates of Siricius, Anastasius, and

Innocentius, when presbyters became the leading force behind the monumentalization of the places of worship.

The accompanying inscriptions commemorating these projects, often preserved only as fragmentary remnants, reveal a deliberate effort to replicate the techniques and style of Filocalus. These inscriptions reflect a conscious attempt by the presbyters commissioning these works to preserve for future generations the ideals embodied in Damasus' literary talent and Filocalus' unparalleled calligraphic craftsmanship.

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Figures

Fig. 1 Fragment of the elogium in honour of Felix and Adautus. Source: C.

Carletti, 'Storia e topografia della catacomba di Commodilla', in J. Deckers, G.

Mietke and A. Weiland, Die Katakombe 'Commodilla'. Repertorium der Malereien

(Vatican City, 1994), p. 11

Fig. 2 Epigram of the presbyter Leo from the cemetery of Hippolytus on the via Tiburtina.

Source: author's photograph, courtesy of the Pontificia Commissione di Archeologia Sacra

Fig. 3 Fragments of the Filocalian script from the Cemetery of Pontianus. Source:

O. Marucchi, 'Notizie', Nuovo bullettino di archeologia cristiana: ufficiale per i resoconti della Commissione di Archeologia Sacra sugli Scavi e su le Scoperte nelle Catacombe Romane (Rome, 1917), p. 111, tab. IX

Fig. 4 Epigram of presbyter Theodorus in the cemetery of Bassilla ad Hermetem on the via Salaria vetus. Source: author's photograph, courtesy of the Pontificia Commissione di Archeologia Sacra

Fig. 5 Inscription of Theodorus from San Lorenzo in Lucina. Source: author's photograph

Fig. 6 a and b Damasus' elogium for the martyrs Nereus and Achilleus in the catacombs of Domitilla (two extant fragments, reconstructed). Source: author's photograph, courtesy of the Pontificia Commissione di Archeologia Sacra

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7 Fragment of an inscription from San Lorenzo in Lucina. Source: author's photograph

Fig. 8 Titulus Sepulchralis of presbyter Timoteus. Source: author's photograph, courtesy of the Pontificia Commissione di Archeologia Sacra

Fig. 9 Funerary inscription with Filocalus' signature. Source: Ch. Stiegemann, M. Kroker and W. Walter (eds), CREDO – Christianisierung Europas im Mittelalter, 2 vols (Petersberg, 2013), vol. 2: Catalogue, p. 79

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¹ For this term see G.B. de Rossi, *La Roma sotterranea christiana*, 3 vols (Rome, 1864), vol. 1, p. 121. For a meticulous analysis of Filocalus' script style and its distinguishing features, see A. Ferrua, *Epigrammata damasiana recensuit et adnotavit Antonius Ferrua. S. J.* (Rome, 1942), pp. 24–8.

² De Rossi, *La Roma*, vol. 1, p. 119; *idem*, 'Epitafio metrico della vergine Irene sorella di Damaso', *Bullettino di archeologia cristiana* (1888–9), p. 147.

³ See de Rossi, *La Roma*, vol. 3, p. 241; also *Bullettino di archeologia cristiana*, p. 20. The first dissenting opinion was expressed by M. Ihm, 'Die Epigramme des Damasus', *Rheinisches Museum für Philologie* 50 (1895), p. 196.

⁴ Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, p. 32.

⁵ Epitaph of Laurentia: *Inscriptiones Christianae urbis Romae: septimo saeculo antiquiores. Nova series*, ed. G.B. de Rossi, A. Ferrua, D. Mazzoleni *et al.*, 10 vols (Vatican City, 1922–92) [hereafter *ICUR*], no. 12416; *Inscriptiones Latinae Christianae Veteres*, ed. E. Diehl (Berlin, 1925) [hereafter *ILCV*], no. 1745; *Carmina Latina Epigraphica*, ed. F. Bücheler and E. Lommatzsch, vol. III: *Supplementum* (Leipzig, 1926), no. 1978; Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, pp. 105–7, no. 10; D. Trout, *Damasus of Rome: The Epigraphic Poetry* (Oxford, 2015), pp. 101–3. Epitaph of Irene: *ICUR* IV, no. 12417; *ILCV*, no. 1696; Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, pp. 107–11, no. 11; D. Trout, 'Fecit ad astra viam: Daughters, Wives, and the Metrical Epitaphs of Late Ancient Rome', *Journal of Early Christian Studies* (2013), p. 22, note 68; Trout, *Damasus of Rome*, pp. 103–10, no. 11.

⁶ Vives argued that this epigram was created after Filocalus' death by another stonecutter.

Ferrua, on the other hand, suggested the opposite, claiming that the workshop imperfections in the script indicate it was produced during the later years of Filocalus' career, when his hands had already lost their former dexterity. Cf. J. Vives, 'Damasus i Filocalus', *Analecta Sacra Tarraconensia* 2 (1926), pp. 491–4, and Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, p. 33.

⁷ Cf. Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, no. 17.1–2, pp. 126–7; no. 41, p. 41; no. 47.2, p. 193–4; no. 62, p. 231–3.

⁸ Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, p. 33: *Iam queramus, quo saltem tempore Damaso Filocalus serviret utrum omne damasianum filocalianum fuerit, semifilocalianum vero non damasianum.*

⁹ The activities of presbyter-founders and builders at the turn of the fourth and fifth centuries are well documented, primarily through epigraphic evidence but also in literary sources such as the *Liber Pontificalis*. Beyond Verus, Theodorus, and Leo – mentioned below – other presbyters actively involved in the monumentalization of sacred spaces in Rome during this period included Vincentius (*ICUR* VI, no. 15762), Ilicius (*ICUR* VII, no. 20059), and, on an especially ambitious scale, Leopardus. Leopardus, in addition to his individual foundations (see *ICUR* X, no. 26673; *ICUR* VII, no. 18370), worked alongside Ilicius and Maximus on construction projects at the titular church of St Pudentiana (see G.B. de Rossi, 'Monumenti del secolo quarto spettanti alla chiesa di S. Pudenziana', *Bullettino di archeologia cristiana* (1867), pp. 51–60). Together with presbyter Ursicinus and Deacon Livianus, he contributed to the construction of a new church, the *titulus Vestinae* (see *Le Liber Pontificalis*, ed. L. Duchesne, 2 vols (Paris, 1886), vol. 1, p. 220). Additionally, Leopardus collaborated with presbyter Paulinus to repair the roof of the Basilica of St Agnes on the *via Nomentana* (see *ibid.*, p. 222). On Leopardus' career see also C. Pietri and L. Pietri (eds), *Prosopographie chrétienne du Bas-Empire, 2 Italie (313–604)* [hereafter *PCBE*], 2 vols (Rome, 1999), vol. 2, s.v. *Leopardus* 2, pp. 1293–4; J. Rüpke, *Fasti Sacerdotum: A Prosopography of Pagan*,

Jewish, and Christian Religious Officials in the City of Rome, 300 BC to AD 499 (Oxford, 2008), s.v. *Leopardus 2*, pp. 763–4.

¹⁰ Trout, *Damasus*, p. 48.

¹¹ Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, no. 18/2, pp. 134–6; no. 70, p. 245. Cf. Trout, *Damasus*, p. 51.

¹² A. Ferrua, ‘Filocalo, l’amante della bella lettera’, *La Civiltà Cattolica* 90 (1939), pp. 40–1; N. Grey, ‘The Filocalian Letter’, *Papers of the British School at Rome* 11 (1956), p. 6.

¹³ Vives ‘Damasus i Filocalus’, *Analecta Sacra Tarraconensia*, p. 486.

¹⁴ Trout, *Damasus*, p. 49.

¹⁵ ‘Über den Chronographen vom J. 354’, ed. T. Mommsen, *Abhandlungen der Königlich Sächsischen Gesellschaft der Wissenschaften*, phil.-hist. Klasse 1 (Leipzig, 1850), pp. 547–693; among the extensive literature on the subject, see J. Divjak and W. Wischmeyer (eds), *Das Kalenderhandbuch von 354 – Der Chronograph des Filocalus*, vol. 1: *Der Bildteil des Chronographen* (Vienna, 2014), esp. pp. 75–7.

¹⁶ A. Petrucci, ‘Per la datazione del ‘Virgilio Augusteo: osservazioni e proposte’, in *Miscellanea in memoria di Giorgio Cencetti* (Turin, 1973), p. 39.

¹⁷ Cf. *ICUR* IV, no. 9515: *Damasi papae cultor atque amator | Furius Dionysius Filocalus scripsit*; *ICUR* I, no. 1486: *scripsit Furius Dion[ysius Filocalus]*.

¹⁸ J. Mallon, *Paléographie Romaine* (Madrid, 1952), p. 57.

¹⁹ Cf., among others, *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum*, Berlin-Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften, 17 vols (Berlin, 1863–) [hereafter *CIL*], *CIL* X, no. 7296: *tituli heic ordinantur et sculpuntur*; *ILCV*, no. 3496: *[---]ridus sc[rip]tor scripsit sculpsitq(ue)*; *CIL* III, no. 633,2: *scripsit et sculpsit*; *CIL* VIII, no. 2482: *sculp(sit) et s(cripsit) Donatus*; *L’Année épigraphique [AE]* (1940), no. 0153: *s[culpsit] / et scri[psit]*; *AE* (1906), no. 0124: *scri(psit) et scul[ps]it*; *AE* (1940), no. 0147: *scrib/[sit]! ---] et sculps[it]*; A. Ferrua and M. Busia, *Tavole*

lusorie epigrafiche (Vatican City, 2001), pp. 155–6, no. 124: *Gauden(t)ius isculse // Leo iscris Leo iscrise*.

²⁰ Petrucci, ‘Per la datazione’, p. 39.

²¹ Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, p. 23.

²² The Passion of Felix and Audactus, most likely written in the seventh century, provides a wealth of topographical information precisely specifying the location where they were executed and where shortly thereafter an underground basilica (hypogean basilica) was erected. See M. Lapidge, *The Roman Martyrs: Introduction, Translations, and Commentary*, (Oxford, 2018), pp. 596–7.

²³ For the Comodilla cemetery, see C. Bellarmino Bagatti, *Il Cimitero di Commodilla* (Rome, 1936), pp. 7–14, 37–58; C. Carletti, ‘Commodillae coemeterium’, in A. La Regina (ed.), *Lexicon Topographicum Urbis Romae: Suburbium*, 5 vols (Rome, 2001–8) [hereafter *LTUR Suburbium*], vol. 2, pp. 134–40.

²⁴ See C. Carletti, ‘Storia e topografia della catacomba di Commodilla’, in J. Deckers, G. Mietke and A. Weiland, *Die Katakombe ‘Commodilla’. Repertorium der Malereien* (Vatican City, 1994), pp. 10–17. For the reconstruction of the tomb of Felix and Audactus, after the works that took place there during the episcopate of Damasus, see *idem*, ‘Commodillae coemeterium’, *LTUR Suburbium*, vol. 2, Fig. 136.

²⁵ F. Bisconti, ‘L’immaginario iconografico della devozione martiriale’, in L. Pani Ermini and P. Siniscalco (eds), *La comunità cristiana di Roma: la sua vita e la sua cultura dalle origini all’Alto Medioevo* (Vatican City, 2000), p. 389. See also D. Nuzzo, *Tipologia sepolcrale delle catacombe romane. I cimiteri ipogei delle vie Ostiense, Ardeatina e Appia* (Oxford, 2000), pp. 23–4, 196–7; P. De Santis, *Sanctorum Monumenta. ‘Aree sacre’ del suburbio di Roma nella documentazione epigrafica (IV–VII secolo)* (Bari, 2010), p. 40.

²⁶ *ICUR* II, no. 6016: *o semel adque iterum vero de nomine felix | qui intemerata fide contempto principe mundi | confessus christum caelestia regna petisti | o vere pretiosa fides cognoscite, fratres | qua ad caelum victor pariter properavit adauctus | presbyter his verus, damaso rectore iubente | composuit tumulum sanctorum limina adornans*. Translation after Trout, *Damasus*, p. 94.

²⁷ On the Chronograph of 354, see ‘Über den Chronographen vom J. 354’, ed. T. Mommsen, *Abhandlungen der Königlich Sächsischen Gesellschaft der Wissenschaften, phil.-hist. Klasse I* (Leipzig, 1850), pp. 547–693; M. Salzman, *On Roman Time. The Codex-Calendar of 354 and the Rhythms of Urban Life in Late Antiquity* (Berkeley, 1990); R.W. Burgess, ‘The Chronograph of 354: Its Manuscripts, Contents, and History’, *Journal of Late Antiquity* 5 (2012), pp. 345–96; *Das Kalenderhandbuch von 354 – Der Chronograph des Filocalus*, ed. J. Divjak and W. Wischmeyer (Vienna, 2014).

²⁸ See *Le liber pontificalis*, ed. Duchesne, p. 276; *Codice topografico della città di Roma*, ed. R. Valentini and G. Zucchetti, 4 vols (Rome, 1942), vol. 2, pp. 89, 110, 153; C. Carletti, ‘“Scrivere i santi”: epigrafia del pellegrinaggio a Roma nei secoli VII–IX’, *Roma fra Occidente e Occidente, XLIX Settimana CISAM* (Spoleto, 2002), pp. 352–5.

²⁹ *Sylloge Laureshamensis* (*ICUR*, s.a., II/1, p. 102, no. 32); *Einsidelnensis* (*ibid.* p. 32, no. 76); *Centulensis* (*ibid.* p. 82, no. 20); and *Turonensis* (*ibid.* p. 67, no. 29).

³⁰ See de Rossi, *La Roma*, vol. 1, p. 119: ‘E minutamente esaminandolo, m’avvidi, ch’era una meschina reliquia del carne damasiano posto un dì al sepolcro de’ martiri Felice e Adauto, ove lo trascrissero gli antiquarii della scuola alcuiniana.’

³¹ M. Ihm, *Damasi epigrammata; accedunt pseudodamasiana aliaque ad Damasiana inlustranda idonea* (Leipzig, 1895), no. 7, pp. 10–12; *ICUR* II, no. 6016; E. Diehl, (ed.), *Inscriptiones Latinae Christianae Veteres* (Berlin, 1961), no. 1982; Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, no. 7, pp. 98–101; Trout, *Damasus*, no. 7, p. 94.

³² Ferrua ('Le tre Rome sotterranee', *La Civiltà Cattolica* 89.3 (1938), p. 412) argued for an earlier chronology, namely the period of Valerian's persecution, when the bodies of the two martyrs would have been buried on private land and venerated within the framework of a private cult: 'around them there were no other graves save for a few burials in the burial plot reserved by the devout *Commodilla sibi et suis fidentibus in Domino*. Only later would it have been opened to the community.' Carletti ('Commodillae coemeterium', p. 136), on the other hand, maintained that dating the martyrdom of Felix and Audactus to the time of Diocletian is more probable, while at the same time emphasizing that the two chronologies are not mutually exclusive when viewed in the context of the site's development – that is, its progression from a strictly private cemetery to a community one.

³³ This was not the last intervention at the tomb of the two martyrs. Evidence for further activity is provided by a fragmentary *elogium* (*ICUR* II, no. 6017), the surviving right-hand portion of which refers to some form of intervention at the tomb of Felix and Audactus, carried out by a certain Felix – *nomen omen* – most likely a presbyter. The loss of the inscription's left side renders the precise nature of this intervention impossible to reconstruct. What is certain, however, is that the inscription dates to the pontificate of Siricius (384–99), as indicated by the formula *salvo Siricio papa*. Whether this refers to the addition of a new structure at the martyrs' tomb or rather to the completion of the work begun by Damasus and Verus cannot be determined with certainty, although Carletti favours the latter interpretation, given the short interval separating the two interventions. See C. Carletti, 'Storia e topografia

della Catacomba di Commodilla’, in Deckers, Mietke and Weiland, *Die Katakombe ‘Commodilla’*, pp. 11–12.

³⁴ Deacon Mercurius was entrusted with supervising the drainage and channelling of spring water on the Vatican Hill. Damasus commemorates his involvement in an epigram dedicated to the project (*ICUR* II, no. 4098). For further details, see R. Krautheimer and W.

Frazer, *Corpus Basilicarum Christianarum Romae*, 5 vols (Vatican City, 1977), vol. 5, pp. 172–3; H. Brandenburg, ‘Das Baptisterium und der Brunnen des Atriums von Alt-St. Peter im Rom’, *Boreas: Münstersche Beiträge zur Archäologie* 26 (2003), pp. 55–71; *idem*, ‘S. Petri Basilica’, in *LTUR Suburbium*, vol. 4, p. 192.

³⁵ Cf. *ICUR* V, no. 13874: [*princip*]e mundi; VI, no. 16963: *contempto principe mundi*; IX, no. 24829: *contempto principe mundi*; IX, no. 23753: *superato principe mundi*; Cf. *ICUR* IX, no. 23753: *confessi Christum*; VII, no. 17669: *quae intermerata fides*; X, no. 26668: *hic victor meruit*.

³⁶ See *ICUR* IV, no. 11078: *Damasus rector titulus post praemia reddit*; IX, no. 23751: *ornavit Damasus tumulum, cognoscite, rector*; IX, no. 23754: *Damasus rector longo post tempore plebis ornavit*.

³⁷ A. Cameron, ‘Filocalus and Melania’, *Classical Philology*, 87 (1992), pp. 142–4.

³⁸ *ICUR* VII, no. 19936: *Laeta deo plebs sancta canat, quod moenia crescunt | Et renovata domus martyri[s Hipp]oliti. | Ornamenta operis surgun[t auctore Dam]aso, | Natus qui antistes sedis a[postolicae]. | Inclita pacificeis facta est [haec aula triumphis] | Servatura decus perpetu[amque fidem]. | Haec omnia nova q(uae)q(ue) vid [[e]] s Le[o presbi]ter hornat*.

³⁹ For fuller discussion, see D. Nuzzo, ‘S. Hippolyti coemeterium’, in *LTUR Suburbium*, vol. 3, pp. 68–75, esp. p. 71.

⁴⁰ Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, no. 75.1, p. 173.

⁴¹ Ferrua *Epigrammata*, no. 18.1. See also A. Felle and V. Ambriola, ‘Falsae a fin di bene.

Copie, manipolazioni, invenzioni devotionis causa tra le epigrafi dei cristiani di Roma’, in S.

Segenni (ed.), *False notizie . . . fake news e storia romana. Falsificazioni antiche,*

falsificazioni moderne (Florence, 2019), pp. 166–7. For photo see

<https://www.edb.uniba.it/epigraph/43202>.

⁴² O. Marucchi, ‘Notizie’, *Nuovo bullettino di archeologia cristiana: ufficiale per i resoconti*

della Commissione di Archeologia Sacra sugli Scavi e su le Scoperte nelle Catacombe

Romane (Rome, 1917), p. 111, tab. IX.

⁴³ Marucchi, ‘Notizie’, p. 111.

⁴⁴ Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, p. 97: *Quod enim tam obvium occurrit presBYTER HOS theodORVS*

patet nullo modo illi spatium aptari posse.

⁴⁵ A. Ferrua, ‘Via Portuense’, *Archivio della Società Romana di storia patria* 111 (1988), p.

13.

⁴⁶ For more on the cemetery of Pontianus, see M. Ricciardi, ‘Pontiani coemeterium’, in *LTUR*

Suburbium, vol. 4, pp. 213–19.

⁴⁷ The *Passio* of Abdon and Sennes is an implausible product of the imagination of an

anonymous author, particularly rich in ahistorical absurdities. See Lapidge, *The Roman*

Martyrs, pp. 325–31.

⁴⁸ See R. Valentini and G. Zucchetti (eds), ‘De Locis Sanctis’, in *Codice topografico della*

città di Roma (Rome, 1942), vol. 2, pp. 107–8; ‘Notitia ecclesiarum urbis Romae’, *ibid.*, p.

92; ‘Itinerarium Malmesburiense’, *ibid.*, p. 151.

⁴⁹ *ICUR* X, no. 26672; Ihm, *Damasi Epigrammata*, no. 96, pp. 97–8; Ferrua, *Epigrammata*,

no. 47.2, pp. 193–4; I. Mossong, *Der Klerus des spätantiken Italiens im Spiegel*

epigraphischer Zeugnisse. Eine soziohistorische Studie (Berlin and Boston, 2022), no. 145, p.

318.

⁵⁰ *ICUR* X, no. 27273, for more see O. Marucchi, ‘Scoperta di antichità cristiane nell’area della basilica suburbana di S. Valentino’, *Bullettino della Commissione archeologica comunale di Roma* 55 (1927), p. 264.

⁵¹ See O. Brandt, ‘Inscription Made by Theodorus Under Pope Siricius (384–399)’, in O. Brandt (ed.), *San Lorenzo in Lucina. The Transformations of a Roman Quarter* (Stockholm, 2012), p. 218.

⁵² This is suggested by remnants of an architrave featuring letters executed in the same script as the inscriptions from the Basilica of St Valentine and San Lorenzo in Lucina (see *ICUR* X, no. 26670.1,2). The stonecutter employing this script was active during the episcopate of Siricius and fulfilled commissions for various presbyters, including Leopardus. His work was primarily concentrated in suburban cemeteries, as evidenced by a dossier of inscriptions written in this semi-Filocalian style. For more details, see A. Blennow and O.

Brandt, ‘Inscriptions and Graffiti in San Lorenzo in Lucina’, in O. Brandt (ed.), *San Lorenzo in Lucina. The Transformations of a Roman Quarter* (Stockholm, 2012), p. 219.

⁵³ Cf. Rüpke, *Fasti Sacerdotum*, s.v. *Theodorus* 5, pp. 918–19.

⁵⁴ C. Pietri, *Roma Christiana: Recherches sur l’Église de Rome, son organisation, sa politique, son idéologie de Miltiade à Sixte III (311–440)*, 2 vols (Rome, 1976), vol. 1, p. 540: ‘il travaille sans doute à l’époque de Sirice ; au demeurant, l’usage eût interdit au clerc de chanter sa propre louange, du vivant de Damase, sans mentionner le pape initiateur des travaux’.

⁵⁵ *PCBE*, vol. 2, s.v. *Theodorus* 2, p. 2166.

⁵⁶ *CIL* VI, no. 41377. For the photograph, see <https://www.edb.uniba.it/epigraph/43136>.

⁵⁷ For the photograph, see <https://www.edb.uniba.it/epigraph/17593>.

⁵⁸ Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, p. 101: *Litterae (. . .) presse filocalianas, ad ultimum Damasi tempus*.

⁵⁹ *ICUR X*, no. 26668: *Extremo tumulus latuit sub aggere montis | hunc Damasus monstrat servat quod membra piorum | te Protum retinet melior sibi regia caeli | sanguine purpureo sequeris Hyacinthe probatus; germani fratres animis ingentibus ambo | hic victor meruit palmam prior ille coronam*. Cf. Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, pp. 190–3, no. 47; Trout, *Damasus of Rome*, pp. 170–1; P. De Santis, *Sanctorum monumenta: ‘aree sacre’ del suburbio di Roma nella documentazione epigrafica (IV–VII secolo)* (Bari, 2010), no. 117. For the photograph, see <https://www.edb.uniba.it/epigraph/11294>.

⁶⁰ Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, p. 191: *Litt. alt. 4,7 circ. filocalianae satis bonae, sed minus solito latae*.

⁶¹ The exact date of Filocalus’ death remains unknown. Ironically, for a calligrapher who designed dozens of epigrams commemorating the deceased, no epitaph was ever left for him. The hypothesis that Filocalus might have died before Damasus was first proposed by Vives (‘Damasus i Filocalus’, *Analecta Sacra Tarraconensia* 2 (1926), pp. 491–4). Ferrua shared a similar view, although the two scholars reached differing conclusions from this premise (see Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, p. 33). Vives argued that the epigram honouring Nereus and Achilles, written in a script that significantly deviates from the idealized Filocalian letters, was likely the work of one of Filocalus’ pupils. For Ferrua, on the other hand, the inferior Filocalian script belonged to the final stage of Filocalus’ career, shortly before his death, when his skills were no longer at their peak.

⁶² Ihm, *Damasi epigrammata*, p. 57, no. 54.

⁶³ Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, p. 209.

⁶⁴ G.B. de Rossi, ‘Sepolcri del secolo ottavo scoperti presso la chiesa di s. Lorenzo in Lucina’, *Bullettino di archeologia cristiana* (1873), pp. 34–5.

⁶⁵ ‘Epistulae imperatorum pontificum aliorum inde ab a. CCCLXVII usque ad a. DLIII datae Avellana quae dicitur collectio’, ed. O. Guenther, in *Corpus Scriptorum Ecclesiasticorum*

Latinorum 35 (Vienna, 1895), p. 2: *coeperunt in basilica Iuli procedere et sibi Ursinum diaconum pontificem in loco Liberii ordinari deposcunt; periuri vero in Lucinis Damasum sibi episcopum in loco Felicis expostulant.*

⁶⁶ Brandt, ‘Inscription’, p. 218.

⁶⁷ For further discussion, see Brandt, ‘Inscription’, p. 219.

⁶⁸ *ICUR* VII, no. 20178; Ihm, *Damasi epigrammata*, p. 43, no. 38; Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, pp. 244–5, no. 70. Cf. Rüpke, *Fasti Sacerdotum*, s.v. *Timoteus*, p. 920; *PCBE*, vol. 2, s.v. *Timoteus*, p. 2203.

⁶⁹ G.B. de Rossi, ‘Il cimitero di s. Ippolito presso la via Tiburtina e la sua principale cripta storica ora dissepolta’, *Bullettino di archeologia cristiana*, (1882), pp. 67–8.

⁷⁰ The *elogium* commissioned by presbyter Andreas has survived, offering a poetic description of the scale of destruction (see *ICUR* VII, no. 19937).

⁷¹ The *Elogium* of Damasus for Hippolytus, see *ICUR* VII, no. 19932; see also the inscription of presbyter Leo, ed. *ICUR* VII, no. 19936, and that of presbyter Ilcius, ed. *ICUR* VII, no. 20059. For the history of the cemetery, see D. Nuzzo, ‘S. Hippolyti coemeterium’, in *LTUR Suburbium*, vol. 3, pp. 68–74.

⁷² De Rossi, ‘Il cimitero di s. Ippolito’, p. 68.

⁷³ For further discussion and examples see A. Rocco, ‘From Officina Lapidaria to D.I.Y. Encoding Inscriptions from the Christian Roman Catacombs’, in A.E. Felle and A. Rocco (eds), *Off the Beaten Track: Epigraphy at the Borders: Proceedings of the VI Eagle International Meeting (24–25 September 2015, Bari, Italy)* (Oxford, 2016), pp. 68–74.

⁷⁴ *ICUR* I, no. 1486; Ferrua, *Epigrammata*, pp. 134–6, no. 18.2. For more see I. Di Stefano Manzella, *Le iscrizioni dei cristiani in Vaticano* (Vatican City, 1997), pp. 260–1.

⁷⁵ Cf. *ICUR* IV, no. 9515: *Damasi papae cultor atque amator* | *Furius Dionysius Filocalus scripsit*; *ICUR* V, no. 13874: [*Damasi epis*]copi cu[ltor atque amator?] | *Furius Dionysius [Philocalus scripsit?]*.

⁷⁶ See note 75.